

Basics of Using New Innovative Technologies in Medicine

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Annotation: The introduction of innovative medical technologies leads to improved disease outcomes and quality of life for patients, but also significantly increases the costs of the healthcare system. The imbalance between limited health care resources and the need for effective health care determines the need to evaluate innovative health technologies before decisions are made on their financing. The article analyzes the characteristics of innovation in the pharmaceutical industry, and also describes approaches to assessing the innovativeness of medical technologies in some foreign countries.

Keywords: innovation, definition of innovation, characteristics of innovation, innovativeness, assessment of the innovativeness of medical technology, innovation in the pharmaceutical industry.

Innovation (Latin *novatio* - renewal) is an innovation, the final result of intellectual activity, successfully brought to the market due to its high efficiency and demand. Innovation is often confused with invention, which is only an intermediate step of innovation. The innovation process looks like this: investment - development of a scientific idea - obtaining a new product - implementation in practice - achieving qualitative improvement. At the same time, medical innovation is the expansion of the knowledge base and the transformation of currently used technological and business models in the interests of more effectively meeting changing needs and expectations. An innovative model of healthcare development should provide for the unity of science, education and practice, international partnership with leading countries and research centers, protection of intellectual property, and development of public-private partnerships. It is necessary to highlight the following directions in innovative activities of the healthcare system:

Medical technological innovations that are associated with the emergence of new methods (methods, techniques) of prevention, diagnosis and treatment based on existing drugs (equipment) or new combinations of their use. Organizational innovations that implement effective restructuring of the health care system, improving the organization of personnel labor and the organizational structure of management. Economic innovations that ensure the introduction of modern methods of planning, financing, stimulating and analyzing the activities of healthcare institutions. Information technology innovations aimed at automating the processes of collecting, processing, and analyzing information flows in the industry. Medical-pharmaceutical, medical-technical innovations, which are a type of medical technological innovation, but which, however, imply the use of new medicines (technical systems) that are competitive in price and basic parameters of medical effectiveness. An innovative model in healthcare must have a special management mechanism that dictates the presence of a dichotomy of two principles:

➤ economic efficiency

- social justice. In medicine, non-market procedures for coordinating the activities of health authorities, primarily from the state, are also needed.

The state must pursue a well-thought-out health policy:

- ✓ responsible for creating conditions for promoting health,
- ✓ fight socially dangerous diseases and prevent them,
- ✓ develop medical science.

It is necessary to make a choice and the optimal combination between budget, insurance, and paid medicine.

In an innovative model of healthcare in a social market economy, “socialization” itself should be dominant, and “marketization” should play a subordinate role. Innovation in the healthcare system is expressed in the following: self-expansion, globality, intelligence, cellularity, competence, technology.

1. Self-expansion is an increase in valuable information (medical science). Constantly in a state of unity and opposition with self-obsolescence 2. Globality is the organization and self-organization of a single international information economic and medical space, so to speak, "social-collective intelligence".
2. Intellectuality is the leading resource of the healthcare system, associated with the growth of qualifications and education of medical personnel capable of leading innovative activities.
3. Cellularity is a single cellular distributed multi-specialized structure of the healthcare system. Formation of cellular-regional medical information structures.
4. Competence is a set of medical knowledge, computer literacy, information culture and thinking style. Health care economics is a branch of the science of economics that studies the place of health care in the national economy, developing methods for the rational use of resources to ensure the protection of public health. **The goal of the innovative healthcare model is to meet the needs of the population for quality medical care.** The WHO global strategy for digital health 2020–2025 notes that technology-enabled care must be accessible to patients. The priorities include security and confidentiality of information, transparency of data processing and strengthening trust in electronic services.. WHO believes that technology-based medicine should develop as an organic ecosystem that will achieve universal health coverage. The organization notes that least developed countries may face barriers to digitalization. To overcome them, it is proposed to develop infrastructure, increase human potential and attract investment.

Conclusion: To summarize, it should be noted that innovative technologies today make a serious contribution to improving the quality of medical care, and this is what requires finding a rational balance between the availability of new drugs and the recognition of their need, including, in particular, the financing of innovative activities.

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